

Predicting Alcohol Consumption in Students Using Data Mining Tool

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Abstract— The alcoholism is a serious problem that affecting both the individual and the society. Alcohol drinking has several short term and future health effects. This paper examines the student alcohol consumption using a publicly available dataset that includes student characteristics and grades. The process using data mining tools and techniques to analyze data for educational purposes is known as educational data mining (EDM). EDM assists academic programs in identifying and revealing hidden patterns in data. These patterns can be used to learn which students consume alcohol and what the impact it has on their academic performance. Our paper contributes to our knowledge of the relationship between student characteristics and alcohol consumption. On a student dataset, this paper compares the performance of the k- Nearest Neighbour (KNN), J48, and Random Forest algorithms.

Keywords— *k-Nearest Neighbor, J48, Random Forest, Weka, Student Alcohol Consumption.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Data mining is a technique for extracting useful information from a large amount of unstructured data. The goal of data mining is to find unexpected/unknown relationships among the data. Educational data mining (also known as EDM) is a branch of data mining that focuses on the development of methods for making discoveries in the unique types of data found in educational datasets, and then applying those methods to better understand students and the environments in which they learn. In data mining, prediction is the process of identifying data points solely based on the description of another data value. It may or may not be related to future events, but the variables used are unknown. The Prediction derives the relationship between something you know and something you need to predict for future reference.

Alcoholism is a serious problem that affects both individuals and society. This has a greater impact on students because they lack the maturity of adults and are not fully prepared to deal with the mental and physical consequences. Drinking alcohol as a teenager can greatly increase the risk of damage to the developing brain, especially as the brain continues to develop into the mid- twenties. It can also lead to later-life alcoholism. Drinking can impair a student's ability to study and earn good grades, as well as negatively impact athletic performance.

This paper examines the student alcohol consumption using a publicly available dataset that includes student characteristics and grades. The study also compares performance of the k- Nearest Neighbours, J48, random forest algorithm.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have already been conducted in this area. a few recent researches work in the area of interest, which are discussed in this section.

In 2016, Mahsa Afsharizadeh and Hossein Ebrahimpour- Komleh used nave bayes to predict the amount of alcohol consumed using five level classification methods. KNN and decision tree. ^[1]

In 2016, Fabio Pagnotta and Mohmmad Amran Hossain plan to use business intelligence and data mining techniques to address student alcohol addiction at the secondary level. ^[2]

Ms. Tismy Devasia, Ms. Vinushree T P, and Mr. Vinayak Hegde proposed a web-based application

in 2016 that used educational data mining and the naive Bayesian mining technique to predict student performance. The results show that the naive Bayesian algorithm outperforms other methods in terms of accuracy.^[3]

Mahdi Nasiri, Fereydoon Vafaei, and Behrouz Minaei describe an educational data mining case study using CRISP methodology in 2012. The findings show that

there are reliable models for predicting educational characteristics.^[4]

Saurabh Pal and Vikas Chaurasia used data mining algorithms such as SMO, bagging, REP tree, and decision tree to analyze the performance of students who consumed alcohol in 2017. The outcome demonstrates that bagging classification is superior to other classification methods.^[5]

Saurabh Pal and Vikas Chaurasia plan to use four decision tree algorithms to predict whether alcohol affects higher education students' performance in 2017. (BFTree, J48, Rep Tree and simple cart). The results show that the BFTree algorithm is mostly effective at classifying and forecasting.^[6]

Akansha Mishra, Rhashi Bansal, and Dr. Shailendra Narayan predict that clustering will be used in educational data mining and learning analysis in 2017.^[7]

Sri Wahyuni used the C4.5 Decision tree data mining technique to analyse drug cases in 2018. The results show that the C4.5 algorithm's Decision Tree is effective in data processing.^[8]

Authpisutaporn, Burit Chonvirachkul, and Daricha Sutivong used decision trees and random forest algorithms to study student alcohol consumption in 2018. The random forest algorithm outperforms the decision tree algorithm, according to the findings.^[9]

In 2018 Shuhaida Ismail and Nik Intan Areena Nik Azlan and Aida Mustapha conduct a comparative study of four classification algorithms, including the decision tree, kNN, random forest, and naive bayes, to predict alcohol consumption. The decision tree produced the highest accuracy values, as shown in the results.^[10]

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for predicting whether or not a student will consume alcohol is divided into the following phases. The main aim of this study is to develop a model of prediction for student's alcohol consumption affect academic performance of students using data mining.^[11]

A. WEKA

In this case, we used the WEKA tool to analyse our data. WEKA is a data mining system that was created by the University of Waikato in New Zealand and uses data mining algorithms. It is an open-source software that includes tools for data pre-processing, machine learning algorithm implementation, and visualization tools, allowing you to create machine learning techniques and apply them to real-world data mining problems [12]. WEKA implements a number of algorithms in each of these categories. You can choose an algorithm and set the desired parameters and run it on the dataset [12]. The statistical output of the model processing would then be provided by WEKA. On the same dataset, the various models can be used. The outputs of various models can then be compared, and the best model that meets your needs can be chosen. As a result, using WEKA speeds up the development of machine learning models in general.

B. Dataset

A number of variables are used to classify alcohol consumption. The dataset used in this study comes from the Kaggle repository, and it contains 395 instances with 33 attributes and a known target class. This data set is used as training data for the classifier.

C. Pre-Processing^[9]

Pre-processing is an important step in data mining. After the data set has been collected, pre-processing methods are used to improve the data set's quality. This includes data cleansing, feature selection, and data compression. Datasets in the real world are prone to noise, inconsistency, and missing values. This is due to the fact that they could have come

from a variety of different sources. The value of high-quality data cannot be overstated. The lower the data quality, the worse the data mining results.

D. Classification Experiment

WEKA is used to carry out the classification experiment. In this paper, we will compare the results of various machine learning algorithms and techniques for mushroom classification, such as J48, KNN, and Random Forest, to see which algorithm has the highest accuracy for identifying student alcohol consumption. Then we look at how other factors can affect the outcome. be used to forecast these levels of alcohol consumption.

E. Evaluation Matrix

To compare classification performance and analyze differences between the k-Nearest Neighbors, J48, and Random Forest, the confusion matrix is used. The classification accuracy, coefficient metric, and time taken to build are among the evaluation metrics used in this study. Precision, recall, fscore, and accuracy are the four metrics. The ratio of correctly classified cases to the total number of misclassified and properly classified cases is known as precision. The percentage of correctly classified cases to the total number of correctly classified and unclassified cases is known as recall. The precision and recall measures are combined in the F-score, which is regarded as a good indicator of their relationship. The ratios of the total number of predictions were correctly calculated, which is the definition of accuracy.

Figure. 1. Student Attributes [13]

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

The main goal is to use a set of parameters to predict whether a student will become addicted to alcohol. The classification of the dataset is done with the Weka tool. In this study, we will use the following algorithms and techniques to classify student alcohol consumption:

A. Classification Algorithms

k-Nearest Neighbour: This method is known as IBk in Weka (Instance Based Learner). Rather than creating a model, the IBk algorithm creates a forecast for a test instance just-in-time. Using a distance measure, the IBk algorithm finds k "close" instances in the training data for each test instance, then generates a prediction based on those selected instances. The K-NN algorithm assumes that the new case/data and existing cases are similar and places the new case in the category that is most similar to the existing categories. This divide n points of data into k clusters, allowing similar points of data to be grouped together.

Fig1: Classification Accuracy by KNN

J48 Algorithm: It's a decision tree technique, and it's one of the most widely used classification techniques in machine learning. System of support

It allows you to anticipate the target. A new dataset record's variable. The J48 Decision Tree Classifier uses a straightforward algorithm. It must first create a decision tree based on the attribute values of the available training dataset before it can classify a new item.

Fig. 2. Classification accuracy by J48

Random Forest: The random forest model consists of a collection of decision trees that are combined to make a prediction. In particular, the random forest prediction will use the value that has the highest probability. The model's highest accumulated confidence across all trees. When the random forest algorithm is used, the system performs better.

Fig. 3. Classification accuracy by Random Forest

I. RESULT

This dataset was classified to distinguish between student alcohol consumption based on their behavioural characteristics. There were 33 nominal attributes in total in the dataset. The results of the testing using the training dataset show that KNN is 100 % as accurate as Random Forest. The J48 has accuracy rate of 89.87 %. In terms of processing speed, however, the KNN method is faster than the J48 and Random Forest methods.

ML TECHNIQUES	ACCURACY
KNN	100%
J48 ALGORITHM	89.87%
RANDOM FOREST	100%

TABLE 1. Performance Comparison Chart

II. CONCLUSION

In this paper we investigated student alcohol consumption and identified factors. For predicting alcohol consumption among students, this study looks at three classification algorithms are random forest, j48, and KNN. It has been discovered that males consume more alcohol than females. We used a student dataset from the Kaggle repository to classify student alcohol consumption using various machine learning techniques. We have found that the KNN performs better than the random forest and j48 for this classification problem.

III. REFERENCES

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